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Code of Justice

A Sector-Specific Quantitative Analysis of Regulatory Gaps in the U.S. Federal Courts for AI Governance

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A top-down view of a desk with a laptop, coffee, flowers, and a candle. The desk is white and cluttered with various items: a silver laptop with a black keyboard, a white coffee cup with a black lid, a bouquet of pink flowers, a lit candle in a glass holder, a white paper bag with a fried chicken sandwich, a black notebook with a white cover, and a clear glass. The background is a plain white wall.

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Motivation & Research Question

Context

AI is diffusing rapidly across sectors (healthcare, finance, technology), but U.S. regulation remains fragmented—agency guidelines, state laws, and judicial interpretation.

Problem

Courts often become de facto AI regulators, creating sector-specific regulatory gaps that yield inconsistent, ambiguous outcomes.

Central Research

Question

How can we systematically measure and compare regulatory ambiguity (“gaps”) in AI-related federal litigation across industry sectors and courts?

Key Concepts

Regulatory Gap Index (RGI)

Composite of citation density, citation diversity, lexical complexity, and hedging frequency.

- Higher RGI → greater interpretive ambiguity in opinion.

Regulatory Gap Percentage (RGP)

Proportion of cases in a sector that exhibit “regulatory failure” (unresolved outcome + low citations + high RGI).

Five Hypotheses

H1 (Sectoral Ambiguity):

RGI/RGP vary by industry

H2 (Citation-Grounding):

Dense/diverse citations reduce ambiguity

H3 (Adjudication Impediment):

High RGI ↓ probability of resolution

H4 (Institutional Drivers):

Court culture/institution more important than text alone

H5 (Court Identity):

Some venues consistently produce higher or lower RGI

Data & Methodology Overview

Data Source:

CourtListener API (v4), 2010 – Jan 2025,
15,583 federal opinions across 17 sectors.

Keyword Strategy:

50 AI-related terms
(e.g., “Machine Learning,” “Data Privacy,”)

Feature Extraction:

Citation density (# citations / # sentences)

Citation diversity (distinct categories:
statutes, rules, acts, cases)

Lexical complexity (unique tokens / total
tokens)

Hedging frequency (% of modal verbs:
may/might/could/should)

RGI Construction

Pipeline:

Winsorize (1st/99th percentiles)

Log-transform citation diversity

Robust scale (median & IQR)

Min-max normalize \Rightarrow

$$RGI = (cd_s + cdiv_s + lc_s + hf_s) / 4$$

Causal Methods:

Inverse Probability Weighting (IPW) for high-RGI
 \rightarrow resolution

Mediation analysis: citations \rightarrow RGI \rightarrow outcome

High-Level Sectoral Results

Median RGI by Sector

- Highest: Technology, Automotive, Manufacturing, Finance & Insurance, Healthcare
- Lowest: Nonprofit/NGO, Agriculture, Public Sector, Hospitality, Real Estate

Trend over Time (2010–2025):

- Tech sector: rising median RGI post-2017 (courts getting more structured/citation-rich).

Highlighted RGP Findings:

- Transportation & Logistics: RGP \approx 6.59% (highest) despite moderate RGI \rightarrow under-grounding/poor resolution.
- Hospitality: RGP \approx 5.08% (small n but high failure).
- Technology: RGP \approx 2.05% (large n but isolated failures).
- Nonprofit/NGO: RGP = 0% despite negative RGI (courts resolve consistently).

Deep Dive – Technology Sector & Court Variability

Tech Sector Highlights:

- Median RGI ≈ 0.031 ; max RGI ≈ 0.048 for undecided cases.
- Max-RGI court: U.S. District Court for S.D. West Virginia; Min-RGI: S.D. Iowa.
- Tech keywords with highest mean RGI: DataProtection, Cybersecurity, DataSecurity.
- Keywords with lowest mean RGI: HateSpeech, IntellectualProperty, DataAnalytics.

Court-Level RGI Trends (2010–2025):

- Federal Circuit & E.D. Texas consistently above sector median post-2020.
- S.D. New York fluctuates below median.
- Convergence toward median after 2020 (more consistency).

Causal Finding (IPW):

- High-RGI courts had a weighted resolution probability of $\sim 77.3\%$ vs. $\sim 79.9\%$ for low-RGI \rightarrow ATE ≈ -1.6 pp.
- Interpretation: More ambiguous courts slightly less likely to resolve cases.

Key Implications & Discussion

Sector specific regulatory gaps

- Regulatory failure often arises from outcome indecision or sparse citations (not just text ambiguity).
- Sectors like Transportation face high failure despite neutral RGI (reflects novel AI usage).

Institutional Context Matters:

- High-RGI courts (e.g., W.D. Texas, S.D. West Virginia) produce highly structured, citation-rich opinions.
- Low-RGI courts (e.g., SCOTUS, 1st Circuit, D.C. District) use minimalist, precedent-driven language.

Citation Practices:

- More citations → lower RGI → higher resolution probability (mediation effect).
- But volume alone isn't enough; outcome clarity and linguistic coherence also key.

Chevron Deference Variation:

- Healthcare: ~121 Chevron cites/1,000 cases; Tech: ~6/1,000.
- Where agency guidance is weak, judicial uncertainty spikes.

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Conclusions & Next Steps

Main Takeaways:

- The RGI/RGP framework provides a replicable, multi-dimensional lens to identify AI regulatory strain.
- Sectoral and court-level analyses reveal pockets of ambiguity even in mature domains.
- Citation richness indirectly reduces ambiguity, improving resolution rates.

Policy Recommendations:

- Develop sector-tailored AI regulations (e.g., Transportation, Hospitality).
- Encourage standardized citation practices & judicial training on AI topics.
- Promote inter-agency coordination to fill gaps where Chevron deference is sparse.

Future Research:

- Expand to state-level and cross-jurisdictional (EU/UK) comparisons.
- Integrate doctrinal/legal scholarship for deeper context.
- Explore non-textual features (e.g., amicus briefs, judge experience).

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For further inquiries and information

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<https://github.com/shru14/Thesis>